

PHENOTYPIC CHARACTERIZATION AND ANTIBIOTIC SUSCEPTIBILITY PATTERN OF STAPHYLOCOCCUS AUREUS CLINICAL ISOLATES

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Abstract: *Staphylococcus aureus* is common cause of hospital acquired infections. A total of 100 clinical isolates of *Staphylococci* were collected. These clinical isolates were identified phenotypically. Isolates were further screened by routine biochemical test and several microbiological diagnostics tests including gelatin hydrolysis, protease, and lipase tests. It was found that 100% of isolates were able to produce gelatin, and 78%, 81%, and 100% of isolates produced urease, lipase, and protease respectively. Latex agglutination test revealed the species *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) with 100% positive result. Antibiogram assessment of *S. aureus* with respect to different antimicrobial agents revealed resistance pattern ranged from 70% to 96%. We also found that a total of 78 strains of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), among these 77% were also resistant to vancomycin. The present investigation is informative and also provides a led for identification and the treatment of MRSA infections.

Index Terms - *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*), *methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), *methicillin sensitive Staphylococcus aureus* (MSSA), *hospital acquired infections* (HAIs).

Introduction

Staphylococcus aureus is a versatile opportunistic human pathogen, and a common cause of hospital acquired infections (HAIs) [1]. Nearly 65% of nosocomial and HAIs are associated with persistent colonization of *S. aureus* [2-4]. It may cause a variety of infections such as skin infections [5], pneumonia, endocarditis, osteomyelitis, and sepsis [6-7]. *Staphylococci* comprise up to two-thirds of all pathogens in orthopedic implant infections [8]. It was estimated that most of surgical site infections (SSI) are caused by *Staphylococci* among these 81% were *S. aureus*, and of these 63% were methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) [9-10]. The incidence of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) infection is increasing [11,8, 9]. The ability of *S. aureus* to produce exoproteins and toxins make them pathogenic. The species is identified on the basis of a variety of conventional physiological or biochemical characters including colony morphology, pigmentation, catalase, free Coagulase, latex agglutination, lipase, and mannitol fermentation. At molecular level *S. aureus* can be identified by reporting taxonomic markers using PCR methods [12-14]

It is difficult to treat infections caused by *S. aureus* because of their resistant pattern. The prevalence of MRSA in HAIs highlights this species as a potential pathogen that is able to survive even in the presence of the antimicrobial agent [15-16]. It was examined that *mecA* gene encode penicillin binding protein (PBP2a) due to which MRSA becomes resistant [14, 17-19]. Selection of an effective antibiotic is important to overcome the burden of MRSA infections world-wide. However, antibiotic responsiveness pattern of MRSA may vary from region to region that's why to treat them different antibiotics included from various class beta-lactams, glycopeptides, lipopeptide, oxazolidones, aminoglycosides, and fluoroquinolones are used [20]. Vancomycin is one of the drugs of choice for MRSA infection. The resistance to vancomycin in *S. aureus* is also on a rise [10, 16]. Therefore, vancomycin resistance is another problem for the treatment of infections caused by this bacterium. The present study aimed to identify and characterize *Staphylococcus aureus* clinical isolates collected in microbiology laboratory, from the wound swab of patients, surgical ward, and orthopaedic ward of AIIMS Hospital, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India, to determine the antibiogram of *S. aureus* strains, and to find out the rate of methicillin and vancomycin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* in hospital-acquired infections.

Materials and Methods

Collection of clinical Isolates-

The present investigation was performed among clinical isolates of *Staphylococci* collected from microbiology laboratory, AIIMS Bhopal. All the clinical isolates were collected aseptically, transferred into mannitol salt agar (MSA) media, HiMedia (Mumbai), and incubated overnight at 37°C. Isolates processed through pure culture technique and stored in nutrient agar at -80°C for further study [21-23].

Isolation and Phenotypic Identification-

Mannitol salt agar is a selective and differential medium used to differentiate *S. aureus* to other *Staphylococcus* species. Clinical isolates were sub-cultured on MSA media for phenotypic and biochemical screening. They were phenotypically characterized as *Staphylococci* through microscopic examination followed by gram staining [24], and then tested for production of catalase, and coagulase. The catalase test was performed, in this test if the organisms are able to produce the catalase enzyme, it detoxifies by breaking down hydrogen peroxide into water and oxygen gas, and oxygen bubbles as output indicates a positive result. *Staphylococcus* spp. and *Micrococcus* spp. are catalase positive. Coagulase is a virulence factor of *S. aureus*. To differentiate *Staphylococcus aureus* coagulase test were performed on strains in this test coagulase enzyme that clots blood plasma. This test differentiates *Staphylococcus aureus* from other coagulase negative *Staphylococcus* species.

1) Slide coagulase test performed on glass slide, is cell bound which requires fibrinogen. Strains which found to be negative with slide coagulase test were confirmed with tube coagulase test. 2) Tube coagulase test free (extracellular) coagulase clots plasma in the absence of calcium. The tube coagulase test with plasma and tubes were examined after 4 h and 24 h of incubation [25]. Test negative tubes at 4 h were re-examined at 24 h because a small population of strains may takes longer than 4 h to form clot. It is the standard test for routine identification of *S. aureus*. In addition rare strains of *S. aureus* are found negative in Coagulase test. Further screened by latex agglutination test, briefly to prepare latex reagent, latex suspension was diluted 1:8 with glycine saline buffer (pH 8.0). Equal volumes of the diluted latex suspension and human plasma (ethylenediaminetetraacetate treated, diluted 1:1,000 with glycine-saline buffer) were incubated for 30 min at 56°C in a shaking bath. The coated particles were washed twice with saline and re-suspended in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH 7.4) containing 0.02% sodium azide and 0.05% human plasma. For slide agglutination test one or two isolated colonies were mixed homogeneously with one drop of saline and one drop of the latex reagent on a glass slide. Slide was rocked backward and forward a few times, the result was read [26-29].

Table 1: Phenotypic characterization of *Staphylococcus aureus*

Source of isolates	Clinical isolates (n)	Colony morphology/Pigmentation			Gram-staining* (%)	Coagulase activity* (%)	Catalase activity* (%)	Latex agglutination* (%)
		Yellow colonies* (%)	Creamy colonies* (%)	White colonies* (%)				
Wound section	5	3 (60)	2 (40)	0 (0)	5 (100)	5 (100)	5 (100)	5 (100)
Surgical Ward	50	20 (40)	12 (24)	18 (36)	50 (100)	50 (100)	45 (90)	50 (100)
Orthopaedic Ward	45	25 (55)	15 (33)	5 (11)	45 (100)	45 (100)	42 (93)	45 (100)
Total	100	48 (48)	29 (29)	23 (23)	100 (100)	100 (100)	92 (92)	100 (100)

*Positive values in number; percentage is presented in parenthesis; (n=number).

Biochemical Characterization-

Clinical isolates were confirmed as *Staphylococcus aureus* by routine biochemical tests. The subculture was made on mannitol salt agar plate; MacConkey, and blood agar plate (Oxoid Ltd. Basingstoke, Hampshire, UK). To distinguish *S. aureus*, various tests were used including biochemical screening based on, gelatinase, urease, lipase production, esculine hydrolysis, protease and mannitol fermentation (Himedia, Mumbai, India) [30] each biochemical medium inoculated with isolated colony. Hemolytic activity was determined on sheep blood agar (15 mL of 5% sheep blood in Trypticase soy agar overlaid on 10 mL of blood agar base) according to Rodgers et al [31].

Antibiotic Susceptibility Pattern-

To analyze the drug resistance pattern of selected strains, antibacterial susceptibility test was performed by Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion using Clinical Laboratory Standard Institute guideline. Commercial disks obtained from HiMedia, (Mumbai) were used [15]. In this experiment the isolated bacterial colony was picked by using a sterile inoculation loop and emulsified in Mueller-Hinton broth (10 ml). The turbidity of bacterial suspension was monitored by evaluating the absorbance of the sample at 600 nm and adjusted the turbidity at 0.5 McFarland. The bacterial suspension was uniformly spread on the Mueller-Hinton agar (MHA) plates and the commercial antibiotic disc HiMedia, Mumbai [28] like, erythromycin (10 µg), chloramphenicol (30µg), ampicillin (30µg), cefoxitin (30µg), azythromycin (30 µg), clindamycin (2µg), gentamicin (10 µg), and tetracycline (30µg) were used. The MHA plates were incubated at 37°C. post 24 h. of incubation the zone of diameter around the colonies was detected and antibiotic sensitivity was analyzed. Result-in the strains were classified as resistant, intermediate and sensitive. Bacterial strains with maximum occurrence of drug resistance frequency were further screened. To identify vancomycin resistant staphylococcus *aureus* (VRSA) and vancomycin sensitive staphylococcus *aureus* (VSSA), minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) of vancomycin was determined by the microbroth dilution method using the Mueller Hinton broth according to the Clinical Laboratory Standards Institute guidelines [32].

Table 2: Biochemical Identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* Clinical Isolates

Source of isolates	Gelatinase activity*(%)	Urease activity*(%)	Mannitol fermentation*(%)	Lipase production*(%)	Esculine hydrolysis* (%)	Protease activity* (%)
Wound section	4 (80)	5 (100)	5 (100)	4 (80)	0 (0)	5 (100)
Surgical Ward	50 (100)	40 (80)	35 (70)	41 (82)	5 (10)	50 (100)
Orthopaedic Ward	45 (100)	33 (73)	34 (76)	36 (80)	5 (11)	45 (100)
Total	100 (100)	78 (78)	73 (73)	81 (81)	10 (10)	100 (100)

*Positive values in number; percentage is presented in parenthesis; (n=number).

Table 3: Hemolytic activity of *Staphylococcus aureus* clinical isolates

Source of the isolates	Sample analyzed*	α hemolysis* (%)	β hemolysis* (%)	γ hemolysis* (%)
Wound section	5	0 (0)	5 (100)	0 (0)
Surgical Ward	50	5 (10)	40 (80)	5 (10)
Orthopaedic Ward	45	0 (0)	45 (100)	0 (0)
Total	100	5 (5)	90 (90)	5 (5)

*Positive values in number; percentage is presented in parenthesis; (n=number).

Table 4: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration of Vancomycin of *Staphylococcus aureus* clinical isolates

Vancomycin MIC (μ g/ml)	MRSA (n= 78)			MSSA (n=22)		
	VRSA *(%)	VISA *(%)	VSSA *(%)	VRSA *(%)	VISA *(%)	VSSA *(%)
0.25	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
0.5	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.2)	0 (0)	0 (0)	12 (54.5)
1	0 (0)	0 (0)	2 (2.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	10 (45.4)
2	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
4	0 (0)	2 (2.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
8	1 (1.2)	13 (16.6)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
16	55 (70.5)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
32	4 (5.1)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)
Total	60 (76.9)	15 (19.2)	3 (3.8)	0 (0)	0 (0)	22 (100)

*Positive values in number; percentage is presented in parenthesis; (n=number).

Antibiotic Susceptibility and Resistance Pattern of *S. aureus*

Figure1: this figure shows antibiotic susceptibility and resistance pattern of clinical strains of *S. aureus*. x-axis shows the antibiotics and y-axis shows percentage of resistance and susceptibility to particular antibiotic, the black color bar represents resistance pattern up to 96% and, gray color textured bar represents sensitivity up to 30% of clinical strains of *S. aureus*.

Figure2: this figure shows prevalence of methicillin resistant staphylococcus aureus (MRSA), black color bar on x-axis shows the clinical isolates* total population (n=100), gray bar shows significantly ($p < .05$) higher percentage of MRSA than MSSA strains (percentage shown by blue bar).

Results

A total of 100 non-duplicate clinical isolates of *Staphylococci* were collected from out-patients in the Microbiology laboratory. A staphylococcal strain produces non white or yellow pigmented colony. Isolated colonies were collected from a selective Mannitol Salt Agar (MSA) media and processed with pure culture technique and then these isolates were further recognized as *Staphylococcus aureus* by different biochemical tests. Gram staining, catalase, coagulase, and latex agglutination were important phenotypic markers to identify the species, *Staphylococcus aureus*. In this study we found that 100% and 92% of isolates were coagulase, and catalase positive respectively. Further examined through latex agglutination test and all isolates (100%) were reported as positive (Table 1).

Staphylococcus aureus secretes an enzyme called gelatinase which liquefy the gelatin protein and in current study it was found that 100% of isolates able to produce gelatinase and protease. Whereas, 78% and 81% of isolates able to produced urease, and lipase respectively. In mannitol fermentation test 73% of isolates were found positive, and 10% were positive with esculine hydrolysis (Table 2).

On blood agar plate, colonies of 90% *S. aureus* found to be frequently surrounded by zones of clear β -hemolysis (Table 3), demonstrating that they can produce hemolysin, 5% surrounded by zones of α -hemolysis, and 5% surrounded by zones of γ -hemolysis. Antibiotic resistant pattern vary from 70% to 96%. We found that *S. aureus* isolates were resistant to erythromycin (96%), chloramphenicol (89%), ampicillin (85%), azythromycin (80%), gentamicin (75%), clindamycin (74%), tetracycline (70%), and cefoxitin (70%) (Fig.1). *Staphylococcus aureus* strains isolated were significantly found to be multidrug resistant. In the present study the prevalence rate of MRSA is 78% among these 60% of the *Staphylococcus aureus* strains were vancomycin resistant (Table 4). The number of MRSA (n=78) was significantly higher than MSSA (n=22) strains ($p < .00001$) shown in figure 2. As per the CLSI guideline strains having a vancomycin MIC of 4–8 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ are vancomycin intermediate, and we found 19.2% strains were vancomycin-intermediate *Staphylococcus aureus* (VISA) (Table 4).

Discussion

In the present study a total of 100 clinical isolates were collected from Wound Section Surgical Wards, and Orthopedic Ward, of Microbiology laboratory, All India Institute of Medical Sciences Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh, India, were validated as *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Studies have linked to an increased risk of *S. aureus* in hospital acquired nosocomial infections as 65% to 80% [3, 33-36]. Gram staining, catalase, coagulase, and latex agglutination test were important phenotypic identifying markers of *Staphylococcus aureus* [14]. In current study we found that 100% isolates were coagulase positive. However, it was confirmed by a latex agglutination test that they are *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Protease of *S. aureus* has long been considered to function as an important virulence factor. A study also found that the secretory protease as a group may contribute to the virulence of *S. aureus* [13]. Karmakar A. reported that, most of the clinical isolates of *S. aureus* are associated with hospital acquired infections and 81% of them were produced protease [14]. In this study we found that 100% of *S. aureus* clinical isolates were able to produce protease. It was hypothesized that these isolates are virulent and could be drug resistant as well.

Over the last three decades methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) has caused major problems in hospitals throughout the world [32], and it may adversely influence treatment outcome, as has previously been shown for staphylococcal bacteraemia [37-39]. Clinical experience suggests that MRSA infections significantly higher than MSSA infections world-wide [8]. Currently we found that out of total 100 isolates, prevalence rate of MRSA was 78%. This finding is supported by Boucher and Corey [40]. The persistent increase in the risk and prevalence of MRSA infections led to the use of glycopeptides as treatment strategy [41]. Vancomycin is one of the drugs of choice for MRSA infection. The resistance to

vancomycin in *S. aureus*, which was once thought to be very less, is also on a rise [10]. So the present study aimed to find out the prevalence rate of MRSA infection and vancomycin resistance in patients. We found that along with 78 MRSA 76.9% were vancomycin resistant also. Maharjan et al. reported higher prevalence of MRSA and significant rate of VRSA from a Hospital in Kathmandu [45]. High proportions of *S. aureus* isolates became MRSA; resistant to all β -lactam antimicrobial agent. In addition, the proportion of VRSA was also high [16]. High prevalence of VRSA among multidrug-resistance MRSA was also found from intensive care units of tertiary care hospitals in Hyderabad, and Al-Jumhuory Teaching Hospital Patients in Mosul, Iraq [43-44]. As shown by our findings, it can be said that MRSA and VRSA are frequently found in hospital environments and are significantly associated with infection.

Conclusions

Our most common pathogen was *Staphylococcus aureus* along with 78% of methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) constituted in hospital acquired infections. Emergence of multiple drug resistant strains like MRSA and VRSA associated infections frequently increases the rate of morbidity and mortality, so early detection and treatment is necessary to overcome the burden. A rapid, identification, based on phenotypic characterization, is suitable in clinical laboratory procedures may aid quick diagnosis. Antibiotic susceptibility pattern assists in the selection of appropriate antimicrobial treatment.

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